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D14.1 WorldFAIR Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANU	Australian National University
APHRC	The African Population and Health Research Centre
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CICAG	Royal Society of Chemistry, Chemical Information and Computer Applications Group
CODATA	the Committee on Data of the International Science Council
CoP	Community of Practice
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DRI	Digital Repository of Ireland
EMBRAPA	Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuária

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESS ERIC	European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GA	Grant Agreement
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums,
GRAF	Global Risk Assessment Framework
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology
ICA	International Council on Archives
ICoEs	International Centres of Excellence
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations
IG	Interest Group
IGAD	Improving Global Agricultural Data
IRDR	Integrated Research on Disaster Risk

ISC	International Science Council
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
KALRO	Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research organisation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSHTM	The London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
ML	Machine Learning
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PID	Personal Identifiable Data
PSDI	Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA P20	Research Data Alliance 20 th Plenary Meeting
SALURBAL	Salud Urbana en América Latina or Urban Health in Latin America
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
TDWG	Taxonomic Databases Working Group, today's Biodiversity Information Standards
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UNStats	United Nations Statistics Division
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the current planning of the WorldFAIR **communication strategy**, intended mostly to direct the activities of WP14 (Outreach, Sustainability and Exploitation).

The main audiences are WP14 and WP1 (Project Management) in directing and informing the expected **communication actions** in the project. However, the document should also be used by the other project participants, as it informs them of the expected communication actions related to their work and guides them on possible engagement activities for their specific target audiences.

The process for the communication strategy drew on **interviews** with seven out of eleven case study Work Packages undertaken in late 2022, identifying the key **communications goals** of each WP, potential **target audiences**, **key stakeholders**, **external communication partners**, and expected **communication channels**. This document is intended to work as a **living document** inside the project and will be **updated regularly** to ensure that the project resources are used in the most efficient way to reach the maximum possible audience for WorldFAIR's outputs.

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1. Introduction

The WorldFAIR project sets out to produce recommendations, interoperability frameworks and guidelines for FAIR data assessment. The WorldFAIR approach, outputs and modes of dissemination will significantly strengthen international cooperation in order to increase and mainstream FAIRness of data and digital objects. Aside from CODATA (the Committee on Data of the International Science Council) and the RDA (Research Data Alliance) Association, who are leading the work, the project consortium (including the associated partners and collaborators) includes a number of authoritative international bodies (e.g., the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, OneGeochemistry), or institutions and projects with international reach (e.g., the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, the 5-year Salud Urbana en América Latina or Urban Health in Latin America (SALURBAL) project, Tonkin+Taylor), such that there is legitimate confidence that the recommendations and outputs will be implemented and have significant impact.

The project aims to join up disconnected initiatives on data management, data stewardship, and FAIR data practices within and across disciplines and internationally by utilising eleven case studies. These case studies, through their focus and the organisations involved, are well placed to do this; they have an important role in engaging their communities with the co-design of the interoperability frameworks and recommendations. The case studies will be assisted by the project leads, CODATA and RDA, and through targeted communication and dissemination to the stakeholder communities identified.

This document outlines the Communication Strategy developed to manage the dissemination and promotion of the project outputs as well as the corresponding dissemination plan. It will outline the available resources that will be leveraged, set out targets and key performance indicators, and provide an overview of the project stakeholders.

2. Communication and Outreach Strategy

The WorldFAIR dissemination, communication and exploitation plan (D14.1) spans the lifetime of the project (24 months). The main points driving the strategy are:

- highlighting the **key message(s)** that each of the case studies needs to deliver, and the specific research question(s) each of the case studies is investigating, taking into consideration both the challenges that may be unique to each discipline, and those relevant to cross-disciplinary research;
- the **impact** and **value** of the work carried out across disciplines and geographies, both in terms of increasing and mainstreaming FAIR-enabling practices and FAIR digital objects, and also the social impact that the 'FAIRification' of data in each discipline can have;
- the **key stakeholders** and **decision makers** for each case study (where such decision

- makers are not already part of the WorldFAIR consortium), and what the **target audience** is for each;
- how the project can support each of the case studies' **unique, individual needs** to ensure that outputs are amplified and disseminated widely.

The WorldFAIR dissemination, communication and exploitation plan outlines the efforts and activities that will be undertaken to promote and amplify the work carried out by each case study, the means utilised to achieve wide dissemination and leveraging of each discipline's existing channels and connections in the relevant data communities. This plan and the communications activities resulting from it will also set the foundation for the **sustainability** of the outputs produced by WorldFAIR.

The plan will be **updated** throughout the duration of the project based on the **evolving needs** of each case study, the project outputs produced, and new amplification opportunities arising. Where significant changes are made to the plan, a new version will be circulated to the project members and uploaded to the WorldFAIR Community Collection on Zenodo¹.

2.1 Objectives and impact

The main objective of the WorldFAIR dissemination strategy is to create cost-effective, efficient, and **targeted communication actions** to support the needs of each case study, enabling them to reach their target groups with their key messages.

A secondary objective is to create the **project brand**, and to establish **visibility and communication channels** with the relevant high-level project-wide stakeholders.

Tertiary objectives are to support the project partners by creating branding and **dissemination materials** needed for their own communication actions, and to **document** and **monitor** the communication actions undertaken by WP14 and other project participants.

Given the global nature of the project, the range of disciplines involved and the authority of the key partners in their respective areas, dissemination of project outputs has the potential for **significant impact** in their respective disciplines. For this reason, this document is based on **feedback** collected directly from the Work Package teams (where possible), ensuring that all of the relevant **target audiences** and key **stakeholders** are being targeted and with the appropriate **means**. Further information on the anticipated impact of the communications activities based on type of activity is outlined in section 4.3 below, 'Engagement and Outreach Tools'.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project/>

2.2 Methodology

Case Study interviews

This strategy was developed based on **interviews** with a sample of seven case studies in late 2022. The purpose of the interviews was to seek the **unique input** of persons carrying out the work, and to inform this strategy and the resulting communications plan with the specific **goals** of each Work Package, their potential **target audiences**, any **existing internal communication plans** and **actions**, and any self-identified **gaps** in their outreach activities and communities, as well as any existing communication and engagement **channels**. The Case Study leads were sent six questions to consider prior to these interviews, which were conducted via Zoom:

1. *What do you want to get out of your participation in the WorldFAIR project?*
2. *What is your main research question?*
3. *What is the impact / value of your research? To whom?*
4. *What community / communities are you trying to reach? Who should know about your case study?*
5. *What networks of dissemination do you have at your disposal (in your institutions, associations, etc.) to promote your work in the WorldFAIR project?*
6. *How can the WorldFAIR project help you in your particular communications needs? [Do you have any audiences that may currently be out of reach that the WorldFAIR project can help you access, or any means/channels of communication in particular that WorldFAIR can provide?]*

The results of these interviews were then used as the core information on which this strategy was built.

Due to time constraints, seven out of the eleven case study leads were interviewed:

- WP3: Chemistry
- WP6: Social Surveys
- WP7: Population Health
- WP8: Urban Health
- WP10: Agricultural Biodiversity
- WP12: Disaster Risk Reduction
- WP13: Cultural Heritage

Further conversations with case study leads focused on the most efficient ways to communicate WP activity and results to the WP14 team, to ensure effective amplification and reporting of project outputs. The agreed methods are listed in section 4.3.2, 'Internal communications coordination', below.

Input from the remaining case studies will be sought and included in the living document version of

this Communication Strategy available via the project internal communication channels.

Analysis

Following the interview process, the WP14 team analysed the results, identifying relevant and common stakeholders across WPs, and proposing effective joint channels when possible.

Limitations

It should be noted that the actions proposed in this document are limited by available time and resources, and one part of the strategy development concentrates on identifying the most efficient (impact/cost) methods and channels to be used.

3. Stakeholders

This section lists the project stakeholders as identified at the Grant Agreement (GA) stage, expanded following the interviews with the seven case studies interviewed thus far. Each stakeholder has unique individual interests and benefits from project outputs in different ways. Therefore, WP14 will utilise appropriate means of communication depending on the target audience / stakeholder group and intended message.

Table 1 below provides a mapping of each stakeholder as per the GA, against their areas of interest within the project and planned means of communication that will be used to target their audience(s).

It should be noted that this table is an initial mapping. Once all interviews have been completed with the remaining WPs, the full list of stakeholders and target audiences will be identified, ranked where appropriate by WP, and the outreach methods will be tailored to these groups more closely. A timeline for each activity will also be defined.

Table 1. WorldFAIR initial stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder / target audience	Stakeholder messaging / benefits	Communication Channels
Individual Researchers & Research Communities	<p>Training materials, best practices and guidelines to support their FAIR data practices.</p> <p>Set of guidelines and recommendations on FAIR data practice and policy in their domain / discipline. Additionally other communities, not directly involved in the project will benefit from the project findings.</p>	<p>Mainly via the relevant WP own connections to researcher communities, supported by Website, social media, videos, events organised by the project and participation in third-party events.</p> <p>Through individual discipline specific case study networks. Use of connection to professional associations when possible or existing.</p>
(e-)Research Infrastructures	Set of interoperability solutions implemented and tested in various discipline-specific scenarios.	Direct project-project connections, presentations/participation in RI relevant conferences/meetings, EOSC channels
Research funders	Recommendations for FAIR data policy, support to facilitate FAIR research outputs for funding grants.	Connection (direct engagement or participation in conferences) to research funders networks via EOSC or Science Europe
Data Stewards and Research support staff	Discipline-specific focused staff will be able to utilise the FIPs at their institutions	Conferences and events, case study specific networks, social media

<p>Polymakers</p>	<p>Recommendations for FAIR data policy making and Recommendations and a framework for FAIR Assessment within Disciplines</p>	<p>Publications, events and conferences</p>
<p>Libraries and other memory institutions, non-profit organisations, community and professional societies</p>	<p>FAIR practices and production of FAIR data across a range of GLAM institutions</p>	<p>Case study-specific contacts, social media, professional societies</p>
<p>Research institutions</p>	<p>Mapping common practice with pilot implementations to clearly define how further organisations can implement recommendations.</p>	<p>Case study-specific contacts, social media, institutional engagement, publications, conferences and events</p>
<p>Data/research initiatives, as well as FAIR Implementation profiles.</p>	<p>Global communities of practice expertise and skills on data interoperability within specific disciplines.</p>	<p>Publications, events and conference attendance</p>
<p>Open Science / Research Clouds / Commons</p>	<p>International technical alignment on FAIR data policy and interoperability. Domain specific and agnostic best practice toolkits and guidelines for take up and implementation.</p>	<p>Publications, events and conference attendance</p>
<p>Healthcare service providers and professionals</p>	<p>Indirect benefit from use of FAIR data in research</p>	<p>Case-study specific contacts, publications, event participation</p>

Repositories/archives	Alignment of repository submission guidelines with FAIR practices/ FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) developed by researchers/research communities	Participation in third-party event and RDA Plenaries, RDA community
Research software Engineers / software developers	Extension of existing tools and software to produce FAIR data and FAIR computational models, and guidance to support this.	Social media, events, publications, RDA (FAIR for Research Software) ² community engagement
Agriculture professionals	Indirect benefit through policies	Case-study specific contacts
Industry / Commercial	Alignment of data sharing/exchange practices, coordination of standards.	Case study-specific contacts, social media, publications, conferences and events, RDA CoPs

4. Communication Plan

The WorldFAIR communication strategic goals will be achieved through the Communication Plan outlined in this document, which aims to disseminate project outputs to the relevant communities and stakeholders, ensuring high visibility, leveraging existing communication channels both through RDA and CODATA and also through project partners.

The Communication Plan is coordinated by WP14, who will liaise regularly with each case study to ensure activity alignment, visibility and reporting. The initial interviews conducted with the case study teams have provided unique insight into each discipline's requirements, needs, gaps and available amplification opportunities.

Each case study also utilises individual communications plans based on the resources available to them locally (at institution or group level), and care will be taken to take these into consideration, to support activities when and as needed and amplify these further through the WorldFAIR channels. The project is in the advantageous position to include a number of authoritative international

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg>

bodies and institutions and projects with international reach; therefore, their role in the community engagement will be of utmost importance.

4.1 Branding and visual identity

The branding of the WorldFAIR project was created as part of Milestone 2. The full report including links to all logo versions, and usage instructions is available on the Zenodo repository³.

The logo(s) produced are intended to be used on all publications, presentations, project outputs as well as outreach collaterals⁴.

This document outlines the full specifications about the branding and presentation of project outputs, both in terms of materials already developed and plans for collateral creation⁵.

The following general guidelines will be followed:

- WorldFAIR logo to be used on all project outputs, presentations, all online presence, videos, etc.
- Templates will be created for poster presentations, which can be adapted by authors/presenters.
- A uniform look and identity will be implemented on all social media presence.
- A uniform look and branding will be used for all printed materials.

The WorldFAIR logo⁶ has been created with the basic project principles in mind: disciplinary research (i.e., multiple uniquely-coloured petals, each symbolising a different scientific field) synthesized and represented in a wheel, i.e., a global, international initiative.

Additional graphics have been created (Figure 2) to be used in all dissemination activities and dissemination materials, depicting the WorldFAIR activities as a whole.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038028>

⁴ In marketing, “collateral” refers to any digital or printed material used to communicate or promote a brand message, products, or services. Marketing collaterals include a variety of formats ranging from printed brochures to point-of-sale posters, videos, e-books, newsletters, graphics, etc.

⁵ Due to resource limitations during the initial months of the project, certain materials (e.g., poster templates, extensive website branding) will be developed after the submission of the current deliverable; the communications plan will be updated accordingly to reflect such endeavours, which will also be included in the final reports (D14.4 and D14.4).

⁶ <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit>

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Figure 1. WorldFAIR logo

Figure 2. WorldFAIR petal diagram

Social media cards

A set of branded social media card templates has been created to be used by the WP14 team for all WorldFAIR content promotion online. Samples of twitter and LinkedIn cards can be seen below (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. WorldFAIR visual identity: Twitter cards

When a crisis occurs, having access to **up-to-date information** is crucial for effective **decision-making**.

In the **disaster risk reduction** space, data can often come from **multiple sources, formats**, and can be either **inconsistent** or **incomplete**.

How do you make sense of a **diverse** range of data in an environment where **sound decision-making** is vital? **Knowledge graphs** can may be the key.

As part of the **ISCRAM** conference alongside **CODATA** and **WorldFair**, **T+T Principal Natural Hazard and Climate Risk Consultant Jill Bolland** is running a workshop on **knowledge graphs** and how they can be applied during a crisis.

Figure 4. WorldFAIR visual identity: LinkedIn cards

4.2 Communication toolkit

The WorldFAIR communication toolkit is in progress at the time of writing, with the following materials planned for development as seen in Table 2. All materials produced throughout the lifetime of the project (contained in Table 2 below) will be added when available at <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit>.

Table 2. WorldFAIR communication toolkit

Material	Description	Status
Information Box for presentations	One slide to be used at every presentation related to WorldFAIR outputs linking to the project.	Completed
Acknowledgement for publications	The following attribution is to be used in all project outputs: "This work was developed as part of the 'Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice' (WorldFAIR), funded by the EC HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 Coordination and Support Action under Grant Agreement No. 101058393. We acknowledge the support provided by the project partners and resources".	Completed
Branded roll-up banner	A roll-up banner to be used at events where WorldFAIR partners participate and/or present project activities / outputs	In progress, to be completed by January 2023.

Branded flyer - template	A reusable template for flyers to be used where WorldFAIR partners participate in events and to be adapted based on promotional needs	In progress, to be completed by Jan 2023.
Zenodo community	https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project/	Completed, managed by the WP1 project coordination team
Collection of collaterals	A collection of marketing collaterals developed throughout the project lifetime.	In progress throughout the project
Collection of press releases	A collection of press releases published throughout the project lifetime.	In progress throughout the project
Collection of newsletters	A collection of all newsletters issued throughout the project lifetime.	In progress throughout the project
Collection of presentations	A collection of all presentations delivered at events by project partners and case studies on project outputs.	In progress throughout the project
Website	Project website to store and disseminate project results and plans: https://worldfair-project.eu/	Completed

The communication toolkit will be continuously updated throughout the project as new materials and collaterals are developed for various purposes; it will be maintained and shared at <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit>.

4.3 Engagement and outreach tools

During the interview process with the case study leads, a number of tools and means of engagement were identified that will be utilised for the promotion and amplification of work conducted by each of the Work Packages. This section will first outline these general communications tools; following that, an assessment of the specific needs of those case studies that participated in the interview process will follow. This section will be updated to include the requirements of all case studies within the project.

4.3.1 General communications channels

Social Media

Three main social media channels have been set up: twitter (@WorldFAIRP), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/worldfair-project/>) and a YouTube channel (to be created) that will be used by the WP14 communications team in the first instance for all amplification purposes across the project.

Planning of a constant stream of project news and updates generated by the WorldFAIR account and then retweeted/reposted by partner institutional accounts, as well as leveraging the personal / institutional accounts of those involved in the project will ensure wide reach.

Websites

The WorldFAIR website was initially set up as part of Milestone 2 and the creation of the project branding, and it is currently under review. It is available at <https://worldfair-project.eu/>, and it will be used as a hub for all project activity, featuring blog posts, event announcements, partner information, case study details and updates, newsletters, presentations and publications, as well as the WorldFAIR communication toolkit.

Content will also be disseminated on the RDA⁷, CODATA⁸ and partner websites.

Monthly Newsletters

Beginning in month 8 and for the duration of the project, a monthly newsletter will be published on the WorldFAIR website, and promoted on the following channels:

- Selected CODATA mailing lists and CODATA website;
- WorldFAIR-all list;
- the Research Data Alliance website and selected relevant RDA Group mailing lists where the content is directly relevant to them.

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org>

⁸ <https://codata.org>

The following channels will also be explored:

- the RESEARCH-DATAMAN@jiscmail.ac.uk mailing list;
- Other mailing lists and contacts provided by the project partners;
- Extended contacts of the project coordinators / work package leaders through other global FAIR data initiatives and projects.

Ultimately, the aim is to create a subscriber base built upon the channels mentioned above as well as any further partnerships and opportunities presented throughout the project lifetime. This subscriber list can then be used to engage the community and stakeholders as part of the sustainability efforts beyond the end of the project.

A template for the monthly newsletter is currently in development and the first newsletter will be in place in **month 8 of the project (i.e. January 2023)**. An Annex section to this current Plan will then be created to include the template, which will include a rough outline of content per month based on forthcoming project deliverables and planned activities and events.

Events

The name WorldFAIR was chosen to evoke the great international technological exhibitions of more optimistic times. CODATA has its origins in the recognition of the need for international cooperation around data collection and data standards that was ignited by the great International Geophysical Year of 1958, while a number of the case study partners and collaborators are also organisations established to promote international cooperation and coordination in given domains (e.g. IUPAC, GBIF). In recent years, the RDA has succeeded in mobilising and bringing together a global research data community. Through its work and activities, the project will nurture that ethos of international cooperation and alignment. The outputs of the project and case studies (recommendations, interoperability frameworks and proposals for FAIR assessment) will be presented as a Great Exhibition, both virtually and at an appropriate event (possibly International Data Week 2023, Salzburg, Austria, please see below for more information) in order to inspire and guide other research areas.

The project has already been discussed with UNESCO. A closing event at UNESCO in Paris and/or in Brussels (during the Belgian presidency) is envisaged.

Both online and in-person events will be utilised for the promotion of work conducted by the WorldFAIR case studies. The presence of WorldFAIR in third-party events will be amplified by the Communications team using the tools described above. Events and webinars will also be organised by the project itself and the Communications team - see section 5, 'Monitoring and performance' for more preliminary information on events in the pipeline.

The communication coordination spreadsheet (see section 4.3.2, 'Internal communications coordination') will also be used to compile upcoming events and presentations organised by either

the project or the partners, and also third-party events, again ensuring the streamlining of activities between all organisations within the project and the Communication team.

CODATA events⁹ and RDA Plenaries¹⁰ and fora will be leveraged. Five WorldFAIR sessions were organised at SciDataCon, part of International Data Week 2022, in Seoul, Republic of Korea and online in June 2022¹¹. The WorldFAIR project held a series of successful workshops between July and October 2022 to introduce and complete FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) with the eleven case study Work Packages. This process culminated in a plenary meeting of the WorldFAIR case studies, “FIPs in WorldFAIR: What have we learnt?”¹² which took place as part of the FAIR Convergence Symposium¹³ in Leiden on 25 October 2022.

A similar event was held as part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Symposium 2022¹⁴ introducing the project, discussing the FIPs outputs and the work of selected case studies. Discussions also aimed to identify more precisely how WorldFAIR’s global and domain perspectives can best contribute to EOSC.

An application for a co-located event at RDA’s 20th Plenary Meeting (March 2023) has been submitted, and at the time of writing is pending acceptance. The goal of this event is to describe the reasoning behind the development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), to give a detailed picture of how it is currently envisioned and what activities, functions, and standards it will encompass, and to provide a current status of the work.

WorldFAIR will also be present at ‘A Decade of Data’: Celebrating 10 Years of the Research Data Alliance’¹⁵. Each month of 2023, from February to November, will be dedicated to a specific theme related to research data management of relevance to the RDA community; a series of sessions will be planned for each of the case studies, aligning to each theme on the RDA’s schedule.

International Data Week 2023, which will take place in Salzburg, Austria 23-26 October, will also be a major event for WorldFAIR. International Data Week combines the RDA Plenary with SciDataCon, the conference organised by CODATA and the World Data System. The high-level theme of the 2023 edition is ‘A Festival of Data’, which fits the double-meaning of the WorldFAIR project name.

Participation in these international events is crucial and creates access to a number of communities.

⁹ <https://codata.org/events>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenary-meetings/future-plenaries>

¹¹ See <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/>

¹² Full milestone report available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7310475>

¹³ <https://codata.org/events/conferences/fair-convergence-symposium-2022/fips-in-worldfair-what-have-we-learnt/>

¹⁴ <https://symposium22.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/worldfair-connecting-eosc-and-global-fair-practices>

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries-events/events/%E2%80%98decade-data%E2%80%99-celebrating-10-years-research-data-alliance>

Other FAIR data projects and initiatives

The WorldFAIR project is closely linked with many other projects and initiatives, and joint communication channels between the projects have a lot of potential for enhancing WorldFAIR impact. A lot of these connections are pre-existing and can be leveraged through the existing connections between partners, or via events organised for this purpose by third parties. Of particular interest are:

- The **FAIR-IMPACT** project¹⁶ has many similarities with WorldFAIR, but is concentrated more on European-level integration, as well as having longer operational time and a wider range of activities. WorldFAIR partners RDA and CODATA are also partners in that project, and joint dissemination activities and sharing of information with the project team has already started. From the point-of-view of communication planning, the connections to their communication team are a priority, and will be created during 2022 and early 2023.
- The **EOSC-FUTURE** project¹⁷ is a major undertaking in the European Open Science Cloud. The RDA is a partner in this project, and connections to their communication teams in EOSC-FUTURE WP10 will be created via this method.
- The **RDA TIGER** project, starting in Jan 2023, will share staff members with WorldFAIR, creating natural connectivity.
- The **EOSC Association**¹⁸ is a major organisation in the field, and is heavily involved in creating a connectivity between the EOSC-related projects (of which WorldFAIR is one). These connections are actively used by the WorldFAIR communication team to disseminate WorldFAIR outputs to these projects.
- The **RDA**¹⁹ in a global sense (**RDA Foundation**, **RDA US**, etc.) is connected via explicit involvement of **RDA Europe** communication staff in these activities.
- **GO FAIR**²⁰, the **World Data System (WDS)**²¹ and other international open data-related initiatives are potential additional channels. The GO FAIR initiative is an author of the FAIR implementation profile (FIP) methodology and so has a strong interest in its further development, and is thus a natural channel for this connectivity. The World Data System is a sister organisation of CODATA, and both are affiliated bodies of the International Science Council.
- Additional interest is based on finding connectivity to funding organisations via e.g. **Science Europe**²² or via the **RDA Funders' Forum**²³.

¹⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu>

¹⁷ <https://eoscfuture.eu>

¹⁸ <https://eosc.eu>

¹⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda>

²⁰ <https://www.go-fair.org>

²¹ <https://worlddatasystem.org>

²² <https://www.scienceeurope.org>

²³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/organisational-bodies/rda-funders-forum>

- Through its parent body, **the International Science Council (ISC)**²⁴, CODATA engages with many international scientific unions (such as IUPAC²⁵), as well as national scientific associations and learned societies.
- The **ISC** has a formal role in the UN science advisory system and both ISC and CODATA work with **UNESCO**²⁶, **UNECE**²⁷, **UNStats**²⁸, **UNDRR**²⁹, **OECD**³⁰ and other intergovernmental bodies. It will be important to communicate the outcomes of WorldFAIR via these channels.
- The **DDI Alliance**³¹ is a global network which connects to the social and economic sciences. CODATA staff members and some other project members are actively involved with the DDI Scientific Board³² and the DDI Training Group³³.

4.3.2 Internal communications coordination

A shared, online spreadsheet³⁴ has been collated and will be circulated to the partners in order to coordinate dissemination activities and to collect all mailing lists, hashtags and accounts relevant for each case study, as well as those of interest project-wide. The information collected on this spreadsheet will ensure that all project outputs promoted locally as well as planned events are visible to the Communications team and vice-versa, thus facilitating the streamlining of all communication and dissemination activities.

A monthly communications drop-in will be set up by WP14, where anyone (WP leads and/or their communications officers where appropriate and available) will be able to attend and provide feedback and information on scheduled activities in need of amplification via the project channels.

4.4 WP3: Chemistry

The overarching goal of this WP is to align chemistry data standards with the FAIR data principles through: development of guidelines, tools and validation services that enable scientists to share and store data in a FAIR manner; addressing gaps in standards that currently restrain chemistry in both academic and industrial areas, in particular taking advantage of developments in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML); and adoption of standards and best practices by critical

²⁴ <https://council.science/>

²⁵ <https://iupac.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.unesco.org/en>

²⁷ <https://unece.org>

²⁸ <https://unstats.un.org/UNSDWebsite>

²⁹ <https://www.undrr.org>

³⁰ <https://www.oecd.org/>

³¹ <https://ddialliance.org>

³² <https://ddialliance.org/scientific-board>

³³ <https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/DDI4/pages/7864375/Training+Working+Group>

³⁴ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1WRSaIMfSy74rVMUfxJfVvdjL7R2HOGxs7QVasNr1ME/edit#gid=0>

stakeholders to significantly increase the amount of chemical data available for all scientific disciplines.

Communication needs and goals

The WP has access to a very wide network. The group has already held two webinars with more to come. The results and presentations of these webinars have been published on Zenodo³⁵. The WP has an extensive plan for upcoming events, which has been shared with WP14 for promotion and amplification.

The case study leads are interested in leveraging the RDA community, which will provide them with access to stakeholder groups that is currently lacking. Such groups include:

- Colleagues that support data work, such as librarians and data stewards, as well as those working on FAIR for Chemistry at the institutional level. WP14 can bridge this gap by linking the work carried out by the WP and the RDA Chemistry Research Data Interest Group³⁶;
- Publishers in chemistry;
- Those involved in a session submitted for RDA P20 relating to chemistry repositories.

Target audiences

Chemistry is a very large and dispersed science, with hundreds of thousands of practising chemists globally. The WP has defined two groups of stakeholders, those connected through the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) and other communities:

- IUPAC has over 50 scientific organisations globally that adhere to its standards, which in turn will be involved in various projects related to data. Therefore, adoption of the WorldFAIR FAIR standards across the IUPAC-affiliated organisations is one way to measure impact.
- IUPAC is also affiliated with the International Younger Chemists Network (IYCN)
- Publishers
- Librarians
- Data Scientists
- Repository staff
- Software developers
- Researchers
- Other disciplines

³⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/fairchemistry>

³⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/chemistry-research-data-interest-group.html>

Partner and third-party initiatives

The WP has access to the following distribution channels:

- American Chemical Society, Division of Chemical Information³⁷
- Royal Society of Chemistry, Chemical Information and Computer Applications Group (CICAG)³⁸
- GDCh German Chemical Society and EUCheMs (European Chemical Societies)³⁹
- NFDI4Chem (German, national-level project, which includes thirty subdisciplines)⁴⁰
- Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI, UK based project)⁴¹
- PubChem⁴²
- RDA Chemistry Research Data IG⁴³

Local outreach networks

- IUPAC's events notifications, social media accounts and calendars
- IUPAC volunteer community

4.5 WP6 Social Surveys

This WP will undertake a comparative study of the data management, harmonisation and integration practices of one of the satellite countries – Australia, through the AUSSI-ESS⁴⁴ – and the core European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC), a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) social science infrastructure. The project will examine both administrative procedures, data and metadata management, and technical environments. It will then leverage the DDI metadata standards to understand how such multi-national collections could be made increasingly interoperable and reusable through shared procedural and technical development, and establish a set of guidelines and tools for the development of cross-national collections into the future.

Communication needs and goals

At present the WP has not identified any gaps or additional needs that the WP14 can provide, apart from the standard support in output and activity reporting and dissemination. The communications

³⁷ <https://www.acscinf.org>

³⁸ <https://www.rsc.org/membership-and-community/connect-with-others/through-interests/interest-groups/cicag>

³⁹ <https://en.gdch.de/home.html>

⁴⁰ <https://www.nfdi4chem.de>

⁴¹ <https://www.psd.ac.uk/>

⁴² <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

⁴³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/chemistry-research-data-interest-group.html>

⁴⁴ <https://ada.edu.au/australian-social-survey-international-ess-aussi-ess/>

plan is a living document, and should further needs arise, these will be communicated to the communications team and implemented into the strategy and plan as needed.

WP6 and WP14 have agreed to meet every quarter to discuss developments and reassess if any specific communications needs have arisen, and WP14 will also join their internal project meetings for further input.

Target audiences

WP6 has defined the following three key stakeholder groups:

- Researchers who would be able to support others in how to conduct surveys of this nature;
- Infrastructure providers who design services that make some of these processes easier;
- Data custodians (archives and repositories) who might preserve and disseminate data, to enable them to improve documentation and support services they provide for users of data.

Partner and third-party Initiatives

The following communications resources are available to WP6 from partner initiatives:

- Communications group at the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)⁴⁵
- Communications experts from other projects.

Additionally, the WP6 members' relationships with the listed organisations will facilitate outreach to the infrastructure providers and data custodians, both of which are key stakeholders for this case study, as represented by:

- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)⁴⁶
- the Research Data Alliance
- Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)⁴⁷
- IASSIST, the International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology, which is holding its 2022 conference in Philadelphia with the theme 'Social Justice from Data'. The three social science and health-related WPs will look to organise a session and/or side event.

The means via which the research community will be approached have not been defined yet formally within the WP. Potential routes include:

⁴⁵ <https://ddialliance.org>

⁴⁶ <https://ardc.edu.au>

⁴⁷ <https://www.cessda.eu>

- Dissemination via the RDA Social Science Research Data IG⁴⁸
- Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)⁴⁹

Local outreach networks

The WP has access to communications resources at the Australian National University (ANU)⁵⁰ that will be leveraged for project outreach.

4.6 WP7 Population Health

This case study will focus on the definition of a suite of aligned standards forming the basis of an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Ready description of data suitable for use across domain and institutional boundaries. It will describe steps for the standards' use within the health domain and indicate the policy actions needed to support convergence on this coordinated set of models for sharing disparate data within health research, sufficient to support modern analysis techniques, and for FAIR data sharing with other domains.

Communication needs and goals

During the initial interview, the WP team stated that their purpose is to attract the interest of researchers who have data for a range of different diseases, and show the value of bringing research and data together for different purposes. Communication efforts will initially focus on the promotion of upcoming presentations and publications.

Target audiences

The case study leads have identified the following specific stakeholders in their field:

- National/regional/community health service providers
- National/regional/community health service policy makers
- Demographers
- Healthcare professionals
- Population Health and Impact researchers
- Other platforms relating to HIV, mental health, etc.
- Researchers

Partner and third-party Initiatives

⁴⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/social-science-research-data-ig>

⁴⁹ <https://sshopencloud.eu>

⁵⁰ <https://www.anu.edu.au>

- The WG has upcoming publications in *Frontiers*⁵¹
- Planned series of presentations at third-party events, which will be communicated to WP14 in due course for amplification.

A proposed side event for the World Science Forum 2022 was accepted but too late, and with too short notice, to be practicable. The WP and the INSPIRE network will explore other opportunities for event-based dissemination, including the possible hosting of a workshop at UNESCO in Nairobi.

Local outreach networks

The WP has identified local communications offices that the WorldFAIR project will be able to leverage:

- The African Population and Health Research Centre (APHRC)⁵²
- The London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)⁵³

4.7 WP8 Urban Health

This Work Package will create guidelines and training in best practices for data provenance management in the urban health sector; the Work Package also intends for guidelines and best practices to be integrated into other disciplines using data in urban planning and management. The guidelines will integrate FAIR and CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance⁵⁴ to address common challenges related to data availability, acquisition, and use; data integration; data quality and completeness; and adequate standardisation processes to make data comparable (across cities within and between countries and regions).

The training component will disseminate the expertise gained during the process of elaborating the guidelines, fostering a community of practice within and across disciplines.

Communication needs and goals

The case study lead on Urban Health has identified communications as a crucial area for their work, given how many domains are involved. Currently, this new research area has many challenges in terms of how its researchers create and share data. Many different types of data are used and contrary to other domains, there are no systematic ways of compiling or using data. Making data FAIR is therefore a challenge.

Within the project, generating a communications strategy that can reach out to their community

⁵¹ <https://www.frontiersin.org>

⁵² <https://aphrc.org>

⁵³ <https://www.lshtm.ac.uk>

⁵⁴ <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

and stakeholders is important.

Currently, the focus is primarily on activities in Latin America, and on reaching other professionals beyond scholars, such as those in healthcare information systems policy-making at national and international levels. Additionally, as other countries are facing the same challenges, the WP hopes to contribute to their local region, and also to share lessons that can be impactful to other regions.

The case study on Urban Health has specifically identified the following two communication priorities where WP14 can provide targeted support:

- Dissemination of results from papers, webinars, etc.
- Through the Urban Health Collaborative at Drexel University⁵⁵, the case study team is proposing a course on 'FAIR implementation for Urban Health' to be included in the Urban Health Summer Institute. This initiative is still at very early stages and approval is pending but, if successful, the WP14 team will dedicate specific resources and efforts to support the dissemination of the course. This activity is planned for June 2023.

Target audience

Initially envisioned as researchers, the WP leads are now extending this to include other target audiences, including data stewards at research performing institutions, as well as those who produce the data at these institutions.

As this WP works mostly with secondary data, the primary goal is reaching those re-using the data. The secondary goal is to reach out to people in health information systems creating the data at a national level (for example, those working in health departments at ministry or governmental level, directors of organisations producing statistical health information, etc.).

Another gap identified by the WP leads is policy makers, as they are considered harder to reach.

Partner and third-party Initiatives

The SALURBAL⁵⁶ project also relates to the WP8 work. This is a Wellcome Trust initiative finishing in 2023, which amongst other things is producing a data platform aiming to make data available to other researchers and stakeholders, making their data visible and shareable.

Local outreach networks

The WP has a number of existing dissemination networks in place, which the WP14 team will leverage and align with.

- Urban Health Network for Latin America and Caribbean⁵⁷

⁵⁵ <https://drexel.edu/uhc>

⁵⁶ <https://www.paho.org/es/temas/salud-urbana>

⁵⁷ <https://drexel.edu/lac>

- The Ubuntu Centre on Racism, Global Movements, and Population Health Equity⁵⁸.

4.8 WP10 Agricultural Biodiversity

RDA's Improving Global Agricultural Data (IGAD) Community of Practice⁵⁹ has been broadly sharing FAIR data best practices and data standards for agricultural research use cases. It will now work with key partners specifically to ensure FAIR data for understanding plant-pollinator interactions, and their outcomes, at biologically-relevant scales for crops. Specifically, this aims at:

1. Ensuring broad participation and alignment of emerging biodiversity interactions data standards for agricultural pollinator and pollination initiatives globally.
2. Establishing concrete guidelines on FAIR data assessment and best practices customised for plant-pollinators and pollination data, metadata and other digital objects.
3. Promoting scalable adoption of these standards and FAIR data best practices by multiple initiatives.

Communication needs and goals

Different audiences produce and consume data in different ways. One key target audience for this WP are agriculture professionals. Getting feedback from these professionals on how they produce and use data, and in what format they need it, is important.

The RDA IGAD Community of Practice (CoP) is a resource that will be leveraged for communications purposes; in this respect, the WP leads have identified the need for the CoP to widen its reach. The WP14 team will support this endeavour by circulating targeted newsletters to the community membership and through the planned WorldFAIR co-located event (pending acceptance) at RDA's 20th Plenary Meeting⁶⁰.

Target audiences

The following key audiences will be targeted in communications:

- Agriculture professionals
- Scientific researchers
- Agricultural departments in national governments
- Decision makers on urban planning and landscaping (particularly in the tropics)
- Community, e.g. through initiatives the WP is involved in, such as Flower-Insect Timed

⁵⁸ <https://drexel.edu/dornsife/research/centers-programs-projects/ubuntu-center>

⁵⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/igad-community-practice>

⁶⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-20th-plenary-meeting-göthenburg-hybrid>

Counts - FIT Count⁶¹, where citizen scientists provide data

- Ecologists and agroecologists interested in species interactions

Partner and third-party Initiatives

WP10 partners have access to or are part of the following collaborations and communities:

- Biodiversity information standards community (TDWG)⁶²
- IGAD Community of Practice
- FAO's Global Action on Pollination Services for Sustainable Agriculture⁶³
- HiveTracks app - supports 40,000 beekeepers across more than 150 countries
- Collaboration with WP9: Biodiversity

The group is currently investigating internally what other partner networks are available, and will report to WP14 in due course.

Local outreach networks

- Personal blogs (with a 5k to 10k per month reader reach)⁶⁴
- EMBRAPA⁶⁵ media resources and GO FAIR Agro Brazil thematic network
- Brazilian Network of Plant-Pollinator Interactions (Rede Brasileira de Interações Planta-Polinizador)⁶⁶
- Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research organisation (KALRO)⁶⁷
- Personal social media, e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter
- DGroup⁶⁸ - Agricultural Biodiversity Plant-Pollinator Data mailing list
- Facebook Groups that WP leads are involved in:
 - Scandinavian Association for Pollination Ecology (714 members)⁶⁹
 - The Buzz on Wild Bees (11,800 members, mainly Australia-focused)⁷⁰
 - Pollinator Research Group (~2,200 members)⁷¹
 - Ecology Group (7,500 members)⁷²

⁶¹ <https://fitcount.ceh.ac.uk>

⁶² <https://www.tdwg.org>

⁶³ <https://www.fao.org/pollination/en>

⁶⁴ <https://jeffollerton.co.uk/blog>

⁶⁵ <https://www.embrapa.br/en/international>

⁶⁶ <https://www.rebipp.org.br>

⁶⁷ <https://www.kalro.org>

⁶⁸ <https://dgroups.org/fao/agribiodata>

⁶⁹ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/78484036619/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/buzzonwildbees>

⁷¹ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/pollinatorproject>

⁷² <https://www.facebook.com/EcologyGroup>

4.9 WP12 Disaster Risk Reduction

The main objective of this WP is to conduct two case studies (Pacific Island and African countries) to address challenges of natural and other hazards, climate change, and sustainability, and how Earth Observation (EO) and other data could be used for undertaking an assessment of systemic, cascading and compounding risks.

Communication needs and goals

The case study leads have multiple important networks of dissemination at their disposal or are directly part of them, both locally and through international, third-party initiatives.

During the interview, the WP12 team identified the need for tailored support in translating technical scientific reports and repackaging them into promotional materials intended for different audiences:

- general population and the global community,
- policy makers and the New Zealand government (Secretary of State, Ministers etc.)

Materials and publications will be shared with WP14 for potential repurposing where possible, and will then be shared through all available WorldFAIR channels, followed by amplification by Tonkin+Taylor and their extended partners. This approach will maximise impact globally.

Target audiences

The WG has identified a number of key groups:

- Humanitarian organisations
- National governments
- Non-governmental organisations

Partner and third-party Initiatives

The case study leads are involved in a number of third-party initiatives, through which they are able to promote their work and project outputs:

- Integrated Research on Disaster Risk (IRDR)⁷³ and IRDR International Centres of Excellence (ICoEs)⁷⁴
- UN Networks
 - United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR)⁷⁵

⁷³ <https://www.irdrinternational.org>

⁷⁴ https://www.irdrinternational.org/irdr_community/icoe

⁷⁵ <https://www.undrr.org>

- Global Risk Assessment Framework (GRAF)⁷⁶
- International Science Council (ISC) and the ISC-UNDRR Expert Working Group on Hazard Information Profiles
- World Meteorological Organisation (WMO)⁷⁷
- CODATA - FAIR Data for Disaster Risk Research⁷⁸
- RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals Interest Group (IG)⁷⁹

Local outreach networks

- Tonkin+Taylor website⁸⁰
- Tonkin+Taylor as well as personal social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook)

4.10 WP13 Cultural Heritage

This case study will assess and map common practices for sharing of cultural heritage data via communities and platforms that predate the FAIR principles; to provide recommendations for how the sharing of cultural heritage data could be made more FAIR (e.g., formats, metadata, vocabularies, PIDs); to implement, test and refine the recommendations for broader applicability in the cultural heritage sector.

Communication needs and goals

The team working on this case study have extensive existing networks in place that will be utilised, and a clear picture of the cultural heritage contacts to which they wish to reach out⁸¹.

The case study team will be leading the communication with their target audience, and will be sharing publishable results with the WP14 team for further amplification via the WorldFAIR channels.

Target audiences

The stakeholders can be divided into two groups: commercial/industry and cultural heritage institutions. The following main stakeholders have been identified:

- Cultural heritage professionals (primary target audience);
- Researchers (secondary target audience);
- Memory institutions (e.g., galleries, museums, archives, etc.);

⁷⁶ <https://www.preventionweb.net/understanding-disaster-risk/graf>

⁷⁷ <https://public.wmo.int/en>

⁷⁸ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/fair-data-for-disaster-risk-research>

⁷⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-sustainable-development-goals-ig>

⁸⁰ <https://www.tonkintaylor.co.nz>

⁸¹ An extensive list of targeted stakeholders has been requested from DRI.

- Digital Repository of Ireland’s (DRI’s) membership;
- Industry partners (including non-profit entities) (e.g., vendors supporting cultural heritage image sharing through software solutions for cultural heritage, or platform providers like Wikimedia) and their influence on community practices.

Partner and third-party Initiatives

Work in this case study will be promoted through the following third-party networks available to the WP:

- Europeana⁸² and Europeana Task Forces and Working Groups⁸³
- The Research Data Alliance
- Irish Museums Association⁸⁴
- International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA)⁸⁵
- International Council on Archives (ICA)⁸⁶
- Higher Education Authority (Ireland)⁸⁷
- Worldwide museums and libraries associations

Leveraging the Digital Repository of Ireland’s Expert Advisory Group and broader connections within the cultural heritage sector the case study leads have opened up a call for participation for a new Working Group with an international membership, tasked with reviewing and refining a set of recommendations for aligning practices across the Cultural Heritage sector with the FAIR Principles. The case study leads are currently in the process of conducting an analysis on gaps in their membership; following the identification of such gaps, the WP14 team will work with WP13 to recruit additional members through leveraging RDA and CODATA channels.

Local outreach networks

The following local means of communication will be utilised for the sharing of case study outputs:

- Digital Repository of Ireland website⁸⁸
- DRI social media accounts (twitter, LinkedIn, etc.)
- Digital Repository of Ireland mailing lists

⁸² <https://www.europeana.eu/en>

⁸³ <https://pro.europeana.eu/europeana-network-association/task-forces>

⁸⁴ <https://www.irishmuseums.org>

⁸⁵ <https://www.ifla.org/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.ica.org/en>

⁸⁷ <https://hea.ie/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.dri.ie>

5. Monitoring and Performance

The milestones and KPIs below were set by the WP14 team as the minimum set of goals that will guarantee dissemination of project findings using the resources and methods available as outlined above. In cases where the milestone is met and opportunities for further dissemination present, the metrics below will be adjusted upwards to reflect that.

Table 3. WorldFAIR Communications milestones

Communication milestone	Task Description	Due Date (month)
1	Interviews promoting the 11 case studies professionally produced and disseminated through available channels (website, social media, etc)	12
2	Minimum 2 press releases and/or articles for the duration of the project	24
3	Creation of four social media accounts (LinkedIn, twitter, YouTube, Facebook)	6
4	3 webinars promoting the work of the Case studies	24
5	2 webinars throughout the lifetime of the project aimed at communications professionals within case study networks aligning strategies and activities	24
6	5 WorldFAIR workshops organised at different stages of the project to provide updates, collect feedback and validation on findings and recommendations	24
7	Dissemination via 5 national, European or international associations contributing to FAIR strategic agendas	24

Table 4. WorldFAIR Communications KPIs

Key Performance Indicator	Observation Method	Target
Average content items per month in social media or	Self-reporting	5

website		
Presentation of WorldFAIR in third-party events during the project	Self-reporting	5
Unique website visits to WorldFAIR Website	Website statistics	1000
Total downloads on the Zenodo repository of WorldFAIR outputs	Website statistics	500

6. Risks

The WP14 team has identified one risk to the successful implementation of the Communication Strategy as presented in this document, which is outlined in Table 5 below.

Table 5. WorldFAIR Risks and Mitigation Strategies

Risk Number	Description	Proposed mitigation measure
1	Low or lack of engagement from the Case Study leads in timely and complete communication to the WP14 team regarding dissemination and amplification needs. Likelihood: Low. Severity: High.	The WP14 team will hold monthly drop-in meetings with the case study teams to ensure that WP14 is informed of all reportable outputs and communication needs. WP14 team members will endeavour to join specific WP sessions periodically to collate information if useful.

7. Sustainability and Exploitation Plan

One of the main goals of WP14 is to support the sustainability and exploitation of project outputs beyond the lifetime of the WorldFAIR project. Based on the key stakeholders identified in this plan, WP14 will interact with the key players (beneficiaries, stakeholders) to identify suitable pathways for post project sustainability for each case study. Furthermore, it will investigate and define a plan for exploitation of the key outputs.

This section will be updated with more concrete information once work on the sustainability plans has begun in the second half of the project.

8. Conclusion

The WorldFAIR dissemination, communication and exploitation plan outlines the strategy, objectives and anticipated impact, as well as the corresponding plan that the WP14 partners will carry out through the duration of the project. The aim is to support the dissemination activities of each of the WPs in a timely and efficient manner.

This plan is a living document, and as such it will be updated regularly as the remaining case studies are interviewed, further stakeholders are identified, additional dissemination opportunities present themselves and those outlined in this document are carried out with reportable results enabling evaluation of the effectiveness (or otherwise) of the identified approaches.
